

Effects of Deforestation and Anthropogenic Aspects on Streamflow in the Mau Forest Catchments in Kenya: Hydrological Modelling of Surface Water Yields from Sondu River Basin

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ABSTRACT: Climatic factors determine the amount and distribution of atmospheric water received at the land surface while the land cover conditions determine the partitioning of this water into different hydrological components and ultimately the catchment surface water yields. This study assessed the effects of deforestation of a tropical catchment on surface water yields to address fluctuating flows of the rivers emanating from Mau Forest, the largest water tower in Kenya. Sondu basin traverses Southwest Mau Forest covering an area of 3500 km². The main channel in the basin flows in a southwest direction into Lake Victoria in an altitudinal range of 2900 to 1130 m a.s.l over a length of 173 km. Different deforestation scenarios over the basin were integrated with climate data to form inputs to a hydrologic model, Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT). Using model outputs, the effects of deforestation on annual and seasonal surface water yields, represented by changes in streamflow volumes under different deforestation scenarios, were evaluated. Deforestation scenarios were derived from a supervised classification scheme of time series of LANDSAT images (1970-2020) to show deforestation trends. Effects of deforestation on the catchment water-yielding capacity were estimated as the ratio of the difference between simulated yields under different deforestation scenarios and those simulated under the pre-deforestation scenario of the 1970s decade. Results show that forest cover declined by 21% and a corresponding growth in land under agriculture by 26% in the period 1970-2020. The decline in forest coverage resulted in an increase in the annual surface water yields of about 23% (from 152 to 187 MCM/year) throughout the period of study. This implies that there is less recharge of groundwater due to decreased infiltration and subsequent storage leading to lower flows during the dry seasons and increased flood frequencies in the basin during the wet seasons. The study has therefore, demonstrated that deforestation has reduced the stability of Mau Forest as a water tower and conservation of the forest will enhance its water-holding capacity thereby ensuring a stable water supply to rivers emanating from it as a way of combating floods and low flows in the basin. The resultant impacts on environment and society are displacements from floods and destruction of properties.

KEYWORDS: Deforestation, Hydrologic Model, Mau Forest, Surface Water Yields, SWAT

INTRODUCTION

Water is a necessary factor for the sustenance of natural ecosystems that support our existence, and also a critical factor in economic productivity, and sustainable livelihoods (1–7). Freshwater has become increasingly scarce as a result of a growing demand for domestic, agricultural, and industrial use coupled with unsustainable use and pollution from anthropogenic activities and land use and land cover (LULC) changes (8–10). Land use, described as the human exploitation and utilization of land resources (11), is an essential part of the terrestrial component of the hydrologic cycle. Changes in land use tend to alter land surface cover which has a significant influence on the catchment hydrology (12).

Pressure on land resources for purposes of providing food, water, and shelter to the ever-growing human population has brought about notable changes in LULC with corresponding impacts on hydrological regimes of watershed areas (13–19). Among the most notable LULC changes that impact a catchment's surface water yield is deforestation; the permanent alteration of a forest to another on-forest use such as agriculture or urban development (20–24). It is well documented that deforestation primarily reduces the base flow from rivers impacting water availability for competing needs by residents (25,26). In regions where there is limited water availability, such changes are likely to add to the scarcity of water supply particularly during the dry seasons. Understanding the

impacts of deforestation on the hydrological process in a catchment area is therefore an essential task for water resources planning for the growing human populations that threaten to stretch this scarce resource to its limit (7,26,27).

Research has demonstrated that as the forest area shrinks and developed land expands, base flow in streams and rivers tends to reduce as a result of reduced recharge of groundwater reservoirs (28–32). There is a need to assess changes in the level of deforestation in a watershed to determine how they impact its surface water yielding capacity which is inversely proportional to the base flow yields (32). Globally, deforestation assessment has been done using multispectral satellite images (33,34). Time series of satellite images is used to derive changes in LULC that include the level of forest cover in a watershed. A series of multispectral LULC classifications are analyzed to determine the inter-annual or inter-decadal changes (18,35).

Several studies on the impacts of deforestation on water resources have been carried out in Kenya. Baker and Miller (2013) found that deforestation within the upper Njoro River catchment brought about increased surface runoff and decreased groundwater recharge. (37) reported that deforestation within the Nyando River catchment resulted in increased surface runoff volumes. (14) reported an increase in surface runoff from about 55% to 68% as agricultural land cover over Nzoia basin increased from about 40% to about 64% and forest cover decreased from about 12% to about 7% between 1973 and 2001. Mungaia (2004) established that the alteration of pastureland and natural forest cover into small-scale farming fields in the upper catchment of Ewaso Ng'iro River resulted in decreased infiltration leading to increased surface runoffs and flash floods.

The Mau Forest Complex (MFC), one of the few remaining natural forests in East Africa, is a contiguous Indigenous forest comprising the largest water tower in Kenya (5,16,39,40) and makes up the upper catchments of the main rivers draining into Lake Victoria from Kenya (41,42). The forest is also home to a rich diversity of natural resources that include, *inter alia*, forest products, micro-climate regulation and water supply (42). Notwithstanding its regional significance as critical a water resource, the forest has experienced widespread deforestation and degradation over the past few decades (42,43). Just like other high water potential areas in Kenya, the MFC is threatened by the growing human population where agriculture and settlements are continually taking high priority (39). This has resulted in large tracts of the forest, previously conserved as protected areas, being excised for settlement and agriculture since the late 1940s (16,43,44). Excision and the extensive encroachment of the forest land have destroyed over 25% of the forest since the year 2000 which explicates the threat of unplanned urban development and population growth from upscaled economic activities (42).

This study attempted to investigate the effects of catchment deforestation on surface water yields in an area that is experiencing rapid socio-economic development coupled with high human population growth (42). Specifically, the study attempted to evaluate how deforestation affects surface water yields by quantifying its contribution to changes in streamflow volumes of River Sondu between the 1970s- and 2020s-decades using SWAT hydrologic model.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Area of study

This study was conducted in Sondu River basin on the western side of Kenya between latitudes 00°23'S and 01°10'S and longitudes 34°46'E and 35°45'E and covering an area of about 3500 km² (Figure 1). River Sondu emanates from Sondu-Miriu Wetlands (45) and is fed by several tributaries, whose source area is the South West Mau block. The longest channel of the river traverses about 173 km from the source areas to Lake Victoria. Sondu River drops about 1800 m between the source areas at about 2900 m and the lake level at about 1130 m above sea level (42,46).

The general land uses in the basin are agriculture, forest, rain-fed shrub crop (tea estates) mainly on the upper elevations bordering the forest, and settlements scattered across the basin (5,47,48). The area under forest comprises the forest reserve and covers about 84000 ha, which is about 20% of the total Mau Forest coverage. Thick Afromontane vegetation typifies the forest reserve (39,42), which plays a critical role in water flow regulation, and comprises of tall, evergreen species that fizzle out to usher in dense bamboo bushes upstream. The areas around the forest experience annual rainfall that ranges between 1500 and 2100 mm. The forest is a source of perennial streams that feed into the main River Sondu, the main source of water to the surrounding tea estates as well as the shores of Lake Victoria South Catchment Area (42,44).

Since the study focused on quantifying how deforestation effects surface water yields, Kiptiget sub-basin (numbers 11 and 12 in Figure 1), was selected as the study unit. South West Mau Forest covers the entire upper catchment of Kiptiget River which

constitutes a critical tributary of the main Sondu River. Any changes in the forest coverage therefore would be reflected in its flow volumes.

Figure 1: Sondu River basin map showing the gauging stations network; numbers 1 to 17 represent the 17 sub-basins that comprise Sondu Basin. Sub-basins 11 and 12, which traverse the South West Mau Forest reserve with their outlet at Kiptiget River Gauging Station (RGS), are the focus of this study

2.2 Assessment of Deforestation

Sondu River basin is home to the large expanse of tea plantations that attract plantation workers from this region and beyond. This has resulted in the basin experiencing rapid socio-economic development that has resulted in unprecedented LULC changes over the last five decades (42). This has seen the SWM forest lose a significant part of its natural cover since the 1970s decade (44). To quantify the level of deforestation of SWM forest as a result of this development, six historical multispectral satellite images of the basin taken by sensors aboard LANDSAT MSS (1973), LANDSAT TM (1986), LANDSAT TM (1995), LANDSAT ETM (2000), LANDSAT ETM+ (2010), and LANDSAT ETM+ (2018) were used. For purposes of this study, the satellite images were used to represent the basin's LULC conditions of the 1970s, 1980s, 1990s, 2000s, 2010s, and 2020s respectively.

The satellite images were obtained from the Department of Resource Survey and Remote Sensing (DRSRS) in false colour composite and were interpreted using a supervised classification scheme (7,46,49,50), guided by the AFRICOVER vegetation classification system (51), to show areas of deforestation in the catchment. Image classification of the false colour composite images of LANDSAT was used to obtain LULC thematic maps (52,53). Temporal changes in LULC between the 1970s and 2000s decades were compared over a 10-year interval and trends in deforestation were evaluated by comparing percentage changes in forest coverage at different times with the baseline forest cover of the 1970s decade. Specifically, the trend of deforestation was analyzed for the number of hectares of forest that were converted to non-forest lands.

2.3 Hydrological Modelling

Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) hydrologic model ((54), is a conceptual physically-based model operating on a daily time-step to simulate the hydrology of a watershed designed for predicting the impacts of catchment management practices, such as LULC change, on water quantity and quality. The model was chosen to simulate streamflow under different forest cover scenarios on account of its suitability for simulation of runoff generation and its ability to integrate different types of spatial data. Model inputs included: Digital Elevation Model (DEM), LULC, soil type and climate data from the basin (15,55).

The global Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) 90 m DEM was applied in the delineation of the watershed into sub-basins and stream networks. The 1973, 1986, 2000, and 2010 LULC, cover maps derived from satellite images were reclassified into four SWAT model format categories comprising agriculture, rainfed shrub crops, open and closed forests. The spatial soil data were geo-processed to a format compatible with ArcSWAT (swat.tamu.edu/software/arcs SWAT/) and then appended to the user soil data set (32,56).

The Model simulated the terrestrial phase of the hydrologic cycle using the water balance concept (Equation 1).

$$SW_t = SW_o + \sum_{i=1}^t (R_{day} - Q_{surf} - E_a - W_{seep} - Q_{gw}) \quad (1)$$

Where SW_t represents the soil water content at time t , SW_o represents the soil water content on day i , t represents time in days, R_{day} represents the amount of rainfall on day i , Q_{surf} represents the amount of runoff on day i , E_a represents the amount of evapotranspiration on day i , W_{seep} represents the amount of water entering the vadoze zone on day i , and Q_{gw} represents the amount of groundwater flow on day i (57).

2.4 Effects of Deforestation on Surface Water Yields

Analyses of the effects of deforestation on surface water yields were carried out by performing four model runs (58) driven by simulated weather data from the Providing Regional Climate for Impact Studies (PRECIS) model for the period 1971 to 2010 and LULC scenarios of the 1970s, 1980s, 1990s, and 2000s decades respectively. For purposes of this study, the four LULC scenarios for the four decades were coded as LU1970s, LU1980s, LU1990s, and LU2000s respectively.

The four model runs were driven by the same time series of weather (daily) and climate (mean monthly) data between 1971 and 2010. From one model run to the next, the only model parameters that were varied were those that were defined by the different LULC scenario maps of the watershed: LU1970s, LU1980s, LU1990s, and LU2000s. Therefore, any changes in the simulated surface water yields from one run to the other were ascribed to variations in the level of forest coverage of the watershed. The effects of deforestation on the catchment surface water yielding capacity were therefore estimated using the ratio of the difference between the simulated streamflow under the LU1980s, LU1990s, and LU2000s forest coverage scenarios to the streamflow under the LU1970s baseline scenario.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Changes in LULC

A total of three main LULC categories were delineated in the upper parts of the basin that mainly comprise the SWM forest; forest land, grassland, and cropland (Figures 2 and 3). Figure 2 shows temporal while Figure 3 shows spatial-temporal changes in the different categories of LULC between the 1970s and the 2020s decades. It was noted from Figure 2 that as of the baseline decade (1970s), the areal extent of these LULC categories were; forest (86.7%), grassland (9.7%), and cropland (3.5%). This coverage has since changed with time where forest coverage declined to an all-time low of 58.9% in the 2010s before rising to settle at 65.7% in the 2020s decade. Grassland, on the other hand, rose to an all-time high of 25.9% in the 2000s decade before declining to settle at an all-time low of 5.1% in the 2020s decade while cropland has consistently risen from an all-time low in the 1970s to an all-time-high of 29.2% in the 2020s. Figure 3 shows that these changes in the LULC categories are mainly concentrated in the northeastern upper parts of the basin. This is a clear indication that the SWM forest reserve has undergone some extent of deforestation where forest land has been converted to grassland and cropland. This has the potential to affect the catchment hydrology leading to changes in surface water yields and rainwater storage in the basin leading to the frequent flooding incidences in the basin witnessed in the last decades.

Encroachment and degazettement of forest reserves for purposes of settling a growing population are the main forces behind the deforestation of the SWM forest reserve (59). The decrease in forest coverage and the corresponding increase in land under agriculture is clear evidence that there has indeed been some deforestation in this watershed where previously land under forest coverage has been cultivated. This deforestation is likely to negatively influence the hydrology of the area through reduced infiltration, and subsequent subsurface storage, thus leading to enhanced surface runoff and increased incidences of flooding as has been experienced lately.

Figure 2: Temporal evolution of the three dominant LULC categories in the South West Mau Forest over six decades; 1970s, 1980s, 1990s, 2000s, 2010s, and 2020s. The area under forest is on a decreasing trend while that under cropland is on an increasing trend.

Table 1 column 2 shows the 1970s baseline LULC status within the southwest Mau Forest reserve while columns 3, 5, 7, 9, and 11 show the status in the 1980s, 1990s, 2000s, 2010s, and 2020s decades respectively. Columns 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 show the percentage changes in LULC coverage concerning the baseline (1970s decade) coverage during the 1980s, 1990s, 2000s, 2010s, and 2020s decades respectively. Positive values in columns 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 signify an increase while negative values signify a decrease in the extent of areal coverage of main categories of LULC in SWM forest reserve compared to the baseline status of the 1970s. Generally, the total forest coverage in the area has been on a declining trend while cropland coverage has been on a continuously increasing rise to over seven times the initial coverage. Grassland coverage has also been on an increasing trend up to the 2000s decade when the trend reversed. These variations are indeed an indication that the area experienced deforestation. A growing population and competing urbanization needs have resulted in reduced forest cover impacting the water flow in the region. Increased anthropogenic activities by forest-dependent communities to increase food production for their livelihoods and economic empowerment contribute to the experienced deforestation (Figure 2 and Table 1).

Table 1: Evolution of different LULC types over the South West Mau Forest from the 1970s to 2020s relative to the 1970s decade

	1970s		1980s		1990s		2000s		2010s		2020s	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
LULC	Ha	Ha	%Var.	Ha	%Var.	Ha	%Var.	Ha	%Var.	Ha	%Vari.	
Forest	73174.4	69353.4	-5.2	64272.4	-12.2	55945.5	-23.5	49638.0	-32.2	55368.8	-24.3	
Grassland	8187.8	11008.9	34.5	13597.0	66.1	21832.0	166.6	12978.6	58.5	4288.6	-47.6	
Cropland	2912.2	3912.2	34.3	6405.0	119.9	6496.9	123.1	21657.9	643.7	24617.0	745.3	

Figure 3: Spatiotemporal evolution of the three dominant LULCs in the South West Mau Forest over six decades; 1970s, 1980s, 1990s, 2000s, 2010s, and 2020s. The forest has over the years been encroached from the northeastern side

3.2 Model Simulations

Figure 4 presents the results of observed and model-simulated mean monthly surface water yields at Kiptiget RGS on the immediate downstream of South West Mau Forest. Based on the results of calibration, with the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 60\%$), the model performance was rated as satisfactory (60), results show that observed and simulated water yields were in agreement. The model captured the patterns of monthly surface water yields quite well in all the months except August where the model indicated a high flow while the observed indicated a low flow. This could be attributed to the fact that the model-simulated flows follow a smoother curve than that of the observed flows leading to a slight lag in the model-simulated flows. The smoothing of the model simulated curve results from the model parameter estimations so that the model only estimates the flows. Overall, the model captured the high and low flows quite well indicating that the model could indeed be used to simulate stream flows in the area.

Figure 4: Comparison of observed and model-simulated monthly surface water yields (MCM) at Kiptiget RGS. Model simulations replicate observations fairly well as shown by the peaks and troughs

Figure 5 presents a correlation of gauge-observed and model-simulated average monthly surface water yields. These results show that observed and simulated mean monthly surface water yields in the area are highly correlated ($r = 0.81$ and $R^2 = 0.66$). This is an affirmation that the model is suitable for the area of study and could therefore be used to simulate surface water yields.

Figure 5: Correlation of mean monthly observed and simulated water yields (cms) at Kiptiget RGS. There is a strong correlation ($r = 0.81$) between simulated and observed surface water yields hence the model is suitable for this area

3.4 Effects of Deforestation on Surface Water Yields

Figure 6 presents percentage variations in mean annual surface water yields under different LULC scenarios based on the 1970s-decade baseline LULC scenario at Kiptiget RGS. These results show that as the forest coverage declined due to conversion to other uses, there was a progressive increase in surface water yields between the 1970s and 2010s decades of up to 23%. This increasing trend in surface water yields was in line with the decreasing trend in forest coverage (Figure 2) where loss of natural forest cover is known to reduce infiltration thereby causing more rainwater to reach the river system as direct surface runoff with very little of it going to groundwater recharge. In such circumstances, flood incidences tend to increase during the wet seasons while low flows during the dry seasons progressively become lower due to the reduced groundwater component of streamflow. Therefore, it was

concluded that deforestation of the area has led to enhanced surface water yields at a rate of 7.5% between the 1970s and 2010s decade. This could explain the increased incidents of floods in the basin as well as the surrounding areas in recent decades.

Figure 6: Variations in the mean annual surface water yields with deforestation relative to the 1970s baseline forest cover scenario. Surface water yields have risen by over 22% of the 1970s-decade levels hence the area is becoming prone to flooding with deforestation

Given that the same climate data were used during all the simulations under different LULC scenarios, observed variations in surface water yields were ascribed to the changes in the level of forest coverage which tends to alter the hydrology of a catchment area. Further, given that the 1970s-decade LULC scenario (LU70s) has the highest forest coverage while the 2000s-decade scenario (LU00s) has the lowest coverage (Figure 2 and Table 1), it was clear that deforestation tends to increase annual surface water yields in the basin by about 7.5% per decade.

The observed increases in surface water yields resulting from deforestation may be attributed to reduced infiltration and evapotranspiration following deforestation of the watershed. While reduced evapotranspiration directly feeds into increasing the yields by reducing the volume of water that is lost back to the atmosphere, reduced infiltration leads to less soil and groundwater recharge and hence less storage during wet seasons. With less soil and groundwater storage, the volume of water flowing in streams during the relatively dry seasons will decrease. This negates the gains of increased yields since less water will be available when it is needed most unless artificial storage reservoirs are availed. Therefore, increases in surface water yields with declining forest coverage are not sustainable as the reduction in infiltration rates tends to reduce the subsurface and groundwater flow components of streamflow that are key in sustaining surface water yields during the dry seasons.

Figure 7 presents a regression of variations in annual surface water yields relative to those of the 1970s on different levels of forest coverage to establish the relative changes in water yields resulting from unit changes in the level of deforestation. These results indicated that indeed annual surface water yields highly depend on the extent of the forest coverage. As the extent of deforestation increased, annual surface water yields also increased. A unit area deforested in the catchment increased annual surface water yields by about 0.9% of the 1970s baseline water yields. Essentially this increase in surface water yields is realized at the expense of groundwater recharge which eventually leads to reduced baseflow. Therefore, deforestation, which is attributable to about 87% of the increase in surface water yields ($R^2 = 0.87$) could explain the high frequency of flood incidents in this area.

Figure 7: Regression of surface water yields on deforestation showing that deforestation accounts for over 87% of the variations in surface water yields

3.6 Conclusion

This study has established that indeed Sondu River basin has experienced deforestation in the last five decades with agriculture being the main driver of deforestation. The focus on improving livelihoods through enhanced food security contributes to deforestation by society as they seek to sustain their existence of a growing population. Overall, the entire basin forest cover decreased from 86.8% to 65.7% between the 1970s and 2020s while cropland has increased from 3.5% to 29.2% in the same period. The study has also shown that effects of deforestation on annual surface water yields cannot be wished away. As the area under natural forest cover decreased, the total annual surface water yields increased. Removal of natural forest cover and its subsequent replacement with other non-forest land uses tends to increase the amount of effective annual rainfall that finds its way to the river system as direct surface runoff; thus, increasing the total annual surface water yields. Deforestation therefore generally tends to increase the total annual surface runoff. This is possibly due to the reduced net capacity of soil and ground water storage leading to more direct surface runoff to the rivers and streams during rainy seasons. The increase in surface runoff increases the risk of flooding in the area following high-magnitude rainfall events.

With the reduced groundwater recharge as a result of decreased infiltration, the base flow of the river system in the area is expected to decrease with time as the groundwater withdrawal as base flow during the relatively dry seasons is not matched by corresponding recharge during the rainy seasons. We may therefore expect reduced dry season flows which will have a negative impact on the water supplies unless artificial storage reservoirs are put in place.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest in as far as this study is concerned.

REFERENCES

- Forero-Ortiz E, Martínez-Gomariz E, Monjo R. Climate Change Implications for Water Availability: A Case Study of Barcelona City. *Sustainability*. 2020 Jan;12(5):1779.
- Gumindoga W, Rwasoka DT, Ncube N, Kaseke E, Dube T. Effect of landcover/land-use changes on water availability in and around Ruti Dam in Nyazvidzi catchment, Zimbabwe. *Water SA*. 2018 Jan;44(1):136–45.

3. Guzha AC, Rufino MC, Okoth S, Jacobs S, Nóbrega RLB. Impacts of land use and land cover change on surface runoff, discharge and low flows: Evidence from East Africa. *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies*. 2018 Feb 1;15:49–67.
4. Kundzewicz ZW, Mata LJ, Arnell N, Döll P, Kabat P, Sçen Z, et al. *Freshwater resources and their management*. 2007;
5. Rwigi SK. *Analysis of Potential Impacts of Climate Change and Deforestation on Surface Water Yields from the Mau Forest Complex Catchments in Kenya*. 2014;
6. Tabari H. Climate change impact on flood and extreme precipitation increases with water availability. *Sci Rep*. 2020 Aug 13;10(1):13768.
7. Wijesekara GN, Gupta A, Valeo C, Hasbani JG, Qiao Y, Delaney P, et al. Assessing the impact of future land-use changes on hydrological processes in the Elbow River watershed in southern Alberta, Canada. *Journal of Hydrology*. 2012; Complete(412–413):220–32.
8. Hasan SS, Zhen L, Miah MdG, Ahamed T, Samie A. Impact of land use change on ecosystem services: A review. *Environmental Development*. 2020 Jun 1;34:100527.
9. Kamamia AW, Mwangi HM, Feger KH, Julich S. Assessing the impact of a multimetric calibration procedure on modelling performance in a headwater catchment in Mau Forest, Kenya. *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies*. 2019 Feb 1;21:80–91.
10. Schuol J, Abbaspour KC, Srinivasan R, Yang H. Estimation of freshwater availability in the West African sub-continent using the SWAT hydrologic model. *Journal of Hydrology*. 2008 Apr;352(1–2):30–49.
11. Nian Y, Li X, Zhou J, Hu X. Impact of land use change on water resource allocation in the middle reaches of the Heihe River Basin in northwestern China. *J Arid Land*. 2014 Jun 1;6(3):273–86.
12. Ortigón YAC, Acosta-Prado JC, Acosta Castellanos PM. Impact of Land Cover Changes on the Availability of Water Resources in the Regional Natural Park Serranía de Las Quinchas. *Sustainability*. 2022 Jan;14(6):3237.
13. Geymen A. IMPACTS OF LAND USE CHANGE ON WATER BASIN USING REMOTE SENSING AND GEOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION SYSTEM. AUBTD-A [Internet]. 2016 Oct 3 [cited 2023 Sep 8];17(3). Available from: <http://dergipark.gov.tr/doi/10.18038/btda.84861>
14. Githui F, Gitau W, Mutua F, Bauwens W. Climate change impact on SWAT simulated streamflow in western Kenya: CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT ON SWAT SIMULATED STREAMFLOW. *Int J Climatol*. 2009 Oct;29(12):1823–34.
15. Gyamfi C, Ndambuki JM, Salim RW. Hydrological Responses to Land Use/Cover Changes in the Olifants Basin, South Africa. *Water*. 2016 Dec;8(12):588.
16. Jebiwott A, Ogendi GM, Agbeja BO, Alo AA, Kibet R. Mapping the trends of forest cover change and associated drivers in Mau Forest, Kenya. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*. 2021 Aug 1;23:100586.
17. te Wierik SA, Cammeraat ELH, Gupta J, Artzy-Randrup YA. Reviewing the Impact of Land Use and Land-Use Change on Moisture Recycling and Precipitation Patterns. *Water Resources Research*. 2021;57(7):e2020WR029234.
18. Wagner PD, Bieger K, Arnold JG, Fohrer N. Representation of hydrological processes in a rural lowland catchment in Northern Germany using SWAT and SWAT+. *Hydrological Processes*. 2022;36(5):e14589.
19. Wang W, Feng Z, Ma M. Climate Changes and Hydrological Processes. *Water*. 2022 Jan;14(23):3922.
20. Chakravarty S, Ghosh SK, Suresh CP, Dey AN, Shukla G, Chakravarty S, et al. Deforestation: Causes, Effects and Control Strategies. In: *Global Perspectives on Sustainable Forest Management* [Internet]. IntechOpen; 2012 [cited 2023 Sep 8]. Available from: <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/36125>
21. FAO. *Global forest resources assessment*. 2005. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations; 2005. 320 p. (FAO forestry paper).
22. Miyamoto M. Poverty reduction saves forests sustainably: Lessons for deforestation policies. *World Development*. 2020 Mar 1;127:104746.
23. N. Sambe L, O. Adeofun C, Dachung G. The Economic and Ecological Effects of Deforestation on the Nigerian Environment. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*. 2018 Jun 7;1(2):1–25.
24. JWajim J. Impacts Of Deforestation On Socio-Economic Development And Environment In Nigeria. *the int jou soc hum inve.*, 2020 Mar 20;7(03):5852–63.

25. Mapulanga AM, Naito H. Effect of deforestation on access to clean drinking water. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 2019 Apr 23;116(17):8249–54.
26. Peña-Arancibia JL, Bruijnzeel LA, Mulligan M, van Dijk AIJM. Forests as ‘sponges’ and ‘pumps’: Assessing the impact of deforestation on dry-season flows across the tropics. *Journal of Hydrology*. 2019 Jul 1;574:946–63.
27. Stonestrom DA, Scanlon BR, Zhang L. Introduction to special section on Impacts of Land Use Change on Water Resources: INTRODUCTION. *Water Resour Res* [Internet]. 2009 Jul [cited 2023 Sep 8];45(7). Available from: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1029/2009WR007937>
28. Atharinafi Z, Wijaya N. Land Use Change and Its Impacts on Surface Runoff in Rural Areas of the Upper Citarum Watershed (Case Study: Cirasea Sub-watershed). *jrcp*. 2021 Jan 2;32(1):36–55.
29. Guzha AC, Rufino MC, Okoth S, Jacobs S, Nóbrega RLB. Impacts of land use and land cover change on surface runoff, discharge and low flows: Evidence from East Africa. *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies*. 2018 Feb 1;15:49–67.
30. Lucas-Borja ME, Carrà BG, Nunes JP, Bernard-Jannin L, Zema DA, Zimbone SM. Impacts of land-use and climate changes on surface runoff in a tropical forest watershed (Brazil). *Hydrological Sciences Journal*. 2020 Aug 17;65(11):1956–73.
31. Potić I, Mihajlović LM, Šimunić V, Čurčić NB, Milinčić M. Deforestation as a Cause of Increased Surface Runoff in the Catchment: Remote Sensing and SWAT Approach—A Case Study of Southern Serbia. *Frontiers in Environmental Science* [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2023 Jun 20];10. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2022.896404>
32. Tadesse W, Whitaker S, Crosson W, Wilson C. Assessing the Impact of Land-Use Land-Cover Change on Stream Water and Sediment Yields at a Watershed Level Using SWAT. *OJMH*. 2015;05(03):68–85.
33. Galiatsatos N, Donoghue DN, Watt P, Bholanath P, Pickering J, Hansen MC, et al. An Assessment of Global Forest Change Datasets for National Forest Monitoring and Reporting. *Remote Sensing*. 2020 Jan;12(11):1790.
34. Kinyanjui MJ. NDVI-based vegetation monitoring in Mau forest complex, Kenya. *African Journal of Ecology*. 2011;49(2):165–74.
35. Sudhakar Reddy C, Saranya KRL, Vazeed Pasha S, Satish KV, Jha CS, Diwakar PG, et al. Assessment and monitoring of deforestation and forest fragmentation in South Asia since the 1930s. *Global and Planetary Change*. 2018 Feb 1;161:132–48.
36. Baker TJ, Miller SN. Using the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) to assess land use impact on water resources in an East African watershed. *Journal of Hydrology*. 2013 Apr;486:100–11.
37. Olang LO, Kundu PM, Ouma G, Fürst J. IMPACTS OF LAND COVER CHANGE SCENARIOS ON STORM RUNOFF GENERATION: A BASIS FOR MANAGEMENT OF THE NYANDO BASIN, KENYA: IMPACTS OF LAND COVER CHANGE SCENARIOS ON STORM RUNOFF GENERATION. *Land Degrad Develop*. 2014 May;25(3):267–77.
38. Mungaia DN. Lessons from two long-term hydrological studies in Kenya and Sri Lanka. 2004 [cited 2023 Sep 8]; Available from: <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/26986>
39. Kinyanjui MJ, Shisanya CA, Nyabuti OK, Waqo WP, Ojwala MA. Assessing Tree Species Dominance along an Agro Ecological Gradient in the Mau Forest Complex, Kenya. *Open Journal of Ecology*. 2014 Aug 14;4(11):662–70.
40. Klopp JM, Sang JK. Maps, Power, and the Destruction of the Mau Forest in Kenya. *Georgetown Journal of International Affairs*. 2011;12(1):125–34.
41. Akanga DO, Dahlin KM, Moore NJ. Accelerating agricultural expansion in the greater Mau Forest Complex, Kenya. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*. 2022 Nov 1;28:100860.
42. Kenya, atlas of our changing environment. Nairobi, Kenya: United Nations Environment Programme; 2009.
43. Kinjanjui JM, Karachi M, Ondimu KN. Natural regeneration and ecological recovery in Mau Forest complex, Kenya. *OJE*. 2013;03(06):417–22.
44. Edwards KA, Blackie JR. 2.1.1 The Kericho Research Project. *East African Agricultural and Forestry Journal*. 1979 Jan 1;43(sup1):43–50.
45. Lake Victoria Basin Commission, GRID-Arendal. Lake Victoria Basin: Atlas of Our Changing Environment. In 2017.
46. Wagner PD, Kumar S, Schneider K. An assessment of land use change impacts on the water resources of the Mula and Mutha Rivers catchment upstream of Pune, India. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*. 2013 Jun 19;17(6):2233–46.

47. Koech NC, Kitheka JU, Otieno H. Influence of Tea Plantations, Forest and Mixed Farming on Stream Flow and Sediment Loads, Case of Sondu Miriu River Basin, Kenya. *Open Journal of Modern Hydrology*. 2022 Oct 8;12(4):155–74.
48. Ochieng WO, Oludhe C, Dulo S, Olaka L. An analytical assessment of climate change trends and their impacts on hydropower in Sondu Miriu River Basin, Kenya. *Afr J Environ Sci Technol*. 2021 Dec 31;15(12):519–28.
49. Li Y, Zhang H, Xue X, Jiang Y, Shen Q. Deep learning for remote sensing image classification: A survey. *WIREs Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*. 2018;8(6):e1264.
50. MoEF. Land Cover and Land cover change Technical manual. 2019.
51. FAO. Land Cover Classification System - Classification concepts Software version 3. 2016;
52. Li M, Zang S, Zhang B, Li S, Wu C. A Review of Remote Sensing Image Classification Techniques: the Role of Spatio-contextual Information. *European Journal of Remote Sensing*. 2014 Jan 1;47(1):389–411.
53. Usha M, Anitha K. Landuse Change Detection through Image Processing and Remote Sensing Approach: A Case Study of Palladam Taluk, Tamil Nadu. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*. 2012;2(4).
54. Arnold JG, Moriasi DN, Gassman PW, Abbaspour KC, White MJ. SWAT: Model use, calibration, and validation. 2012;
55. Kiros G, Shetty A, Nandagiri L. Performance Evaluation of SWAT Model for Land Use and Land Cover Changes under different Climatic Conditions: A Review. *Hydrol Current Res [Internet]*. 2015 [cited 2023 Sep 9];06(03). Available from: <https://www.omicsonline.org/open-access/performance-evaluation-of-swat-model-for-land-use-and-land-coverchanges-under-different-climatic-conditions-a-review-2157-7587-1000216.php?aid=64074>
56. Rwigi SK, Muthama JN, Opere AO, Opijah FJ, Gichuki FN. Simulated Impacts of Climate Change on Surface Water Yields over the Sondu Basin in Kenya. *Int J Innov Educ Res*. 2016 Aug 31;4(8):161–73.
57. Neitch, J. G Arnold, J. R Kiniry, J. R Williams. Soil and Water Assessment Tool Theoretical Documentation Version 2009. 2011.
58. Winchell M, Srinivasan R, Luzio MD, J. Arnold. ARCSWAT INTERFACE FOR SWAT2012 USER'S GUIDE. 2013;
59. Kenya, atlas of our changing environment. Nairobi, Kenya: United Nations Environment Programme; 2009.
60. Moriasi D. N, M. W. Gitau, N. Pai, P. Daggupati. Hydrologic and Water Quality Models: Performance Measures and Evaluation Criteria. *Trans ASABE*. 2015 Dec 30;58(6):1763–85.

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